

A Mini-Review of RNG Theory

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Abstract

This mini-review presents literature excerpts from one important and influential 1992 academic statistical text book by Clarke et al., as well as original commentary, discussion and new formulations concerning the matter of Random Number Generators (RNGs) and their evaluation.

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Review of “A BASIC COURSE IN STATISTICS (3rd Edtn)” — G.M. Clarke & D. Cooke

First, in **Chapter 3, Section 4** of [1], which treats of **Random Numbers**, we learn that:

Drawing numbers from a hat or throwing dice can be used to choose random samples.

Further, we learn that

For greater convenience, statisticians prefer to use random numbers that come from tables or have been generated by computer.

Thus, or rather, we basically see that professionals shall either source their random numbers from trusted static or dynamic **Random Number Generators** (RNGs).

Thus we can distinguish between RNGs by the following basic classification:

1. **Static RNG:** one such as Random Number Tables — printed on paper, or electronic, but essentially fixed.
2. **Dynamic RNG:** one such as Random Number Generator Programs — especially as software algorithms able to run on actual computers, and also capable of dynamic number generation (arguably, the only electronic or algorithmic way to arrive at **true random number generation**¹).

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¹But, it is not necessarily true that all or any electronic RNG is automatically a **trNG** — more about this later.

We further learn that...

Random number tables contain lists of the digits 0-9 in random order.

0.0.1 Concerning [Implementing] Physical Random Number Generators

We learn that [good] random sampling requires that the method used (such as in the random selection of days in a year: 001-365) gives all the valid options equal chance of occurrence or rather, equal chance of being in the sample.

Thus, if a method would make certain numbers more likely to appear in the generated/sample results than others, then such a method would not only be biased, but would not be true to the principle of random sampling.

One method (practical), of generating random numbers that is described in the textbook, utilizes a circular disc with 10 equal divisions on it, and with the digits 0-9 mapped to/inscribed on each of these sectors. The wheel then rotates about a pivot at its center, at high speed and so that, every once in a while, a flash from a lamp lights it up in a single section, so that an observer (human), positioned before the wheel and watching it, then reads the number/digit that appears at a position indicated by a fixed pointer.

In a way, this proposed method feels like a kind of “roulette wheel” or perhaps the “wheel of fortune” game or concept popular in casinos and at birthday parties of statisticians.

Further, and with some adjustments (or “normalization”) to the generated numbers, another method, first proposed by, and attributed to Fisher & Yates, is based on selecting the 15th - 19th digits from a table of logarithms expressed to 20 [decimal] places. However, it was found that numbers generated thus, contained many “6” entries in them. and so, warranted that the outputs of the generator be adjusted to be *more random*.

0.0.2 Concerning The Notion of Random Numbers

G.M. Clarke et al. further indicates that

We all have an intuitive idea what random numbers are but it is impossible to give a precise definition.

Further, they assert...

The best we can do is to think of the properties that random numbers ought have, and check whether any particular list [of random numbers] has these properties.

Though we might not delve into it here, right now, the reviewer wishes to argue against Clarke et al’s line of thinking in [1], if not for any other reason, perhaps because a lot concerning the theory and practice of RNGs has been advanced in both theory and practice since their work was first published — see [2] as an example, and that we not only have the [right] theory and tools to rigorously define and treat of RNGs at the moment, but that such new mathematics as transformatomics[3][4] shall soon enable us to have a universally

usable, pure mathematical and philosophically meaningful working definition of a random number generator². In recent works such as the first book demonstrating how to apply transformatics in Genetics[4], we get to also glimpse of, and learn about a potentially fundamental reference implementation of not only a random number generator, but also a formal, mathematical definition of and reference implementation of a **Random Sequence Generator** (RSG) — refer to **Chapter 8** in [4].

0.0.3 Concerning Properties of Good RNGs

On the matter of how to go about evaluating or objectively discriminating between different methods and implementations of random number generators, this book has this to say concerning the presented practical digit generation methods:

Obviously, the ten digits (0-9) ought to occur with approximately equal frequency, and there should not be long runs of one [or the same] digit.

0.1 Concerning Pseudo-Random Numbers

So, in [1], the authors present the following important problem:

How can a computer be made to produce random numbers?

Though they themselves use it in several problems and examples throughout the book, we later see the authors arguing against any methods relying on the literal storage of random numbers (such as is the case when random number tables are stored/printed in a book). It is argued, that such an approach would be wasteful of resources (such as memory in the case of electronic storage of random numbers, or space/paper in the case of printed work), but also that such methods might not be efficient or even deterministic/predictable. So, instead, it is proposed:

One requires a method, which must work according to a fixed rule and therefore be deterministic, which will produce numbers that have properties of true random numbers.

We thus can distill a few of the essential desirable properties of a good RNG as the following:

1. **Deterministic:** essentially, that we can predict (if we need to), what number or outputs the generator would produce given some initial conditions (such as a particular seed for example).
2. **Formulaic/Algorithmic:** that the generator be the kind we can express or specify using a computable definition, or which we can correctly express as a computer program or software. But also, as we find in transformatics, such could be any method or generator we can express entirely or completely using just simple pure mathematics or an algebraic definition.

²For those not aware, this concept is too fundamental, too important in many fields and lines of scientific and mathematical inquiry, such as exhibited in and presented in various treatments in the author's work on new mathematics for geneticists[4].

3. **True:** basically, that, the generator should be able to **consistently** produce **true random numbers**[2].

And talking of which, in **Chapter 3, Section 5** of this somewhat elementary book, we find proposed one interesting algorithmic RNG that leverages basic arithmetic operations via a formula:

$$X_{n+1} = aX_n + b \pmod{m} \quad (1)$$

Of whose useful properties, the **production** expressed in **Equation 1** is not only recursive, but is also not cyclic.

One should note that, this method calls for a somewhat arbitrary, even though useful choice of [meaningful] numeric parameters — constants basically, for the variables a , b and m , and then, starting by fixing X_0 — the “start” or “seed”, then X_{n+1} can then be computed using the given formula.

However, since this is a method meant for [especially] computers, sufficient optimizations could include selection of values for a , b and m such that the RNG always produces random numbers between 0 and 1 (*pure fractional*[5]), and these can then be used to generate [whole, or rather *pure*[5]] numbers in any range.

Finally, note that, to be realistic, the RNG depicted in **Equation 1**, despite its attractiveness and mathematical simplicity, would be as good as the source of the *initial seed*. This, because, if the seed source is unreliable or unbiased, then also the results of the RNG would be³.

0.2 On Random Digit Generation

First, Clarke et al., in **Chapter 18, Section 1**, advance the following informative definition concerning the concept of a **sequence of random digits**:

Definition (Sequence of Random Digits): A set of digits is a sequence of random digits if every position in the sequence is likely to be occupied by any one of the digits being used, and positions are filled independently.

Thus, and in general, we might talk of random number sequences as having the following properties:

1. **Uniform Distribution:** basically, that the members in the sequence have equal likelihood of occurrence across the sequence.
2. **Statistical Independence:** that the occurrence of any member in such a sequence has no dependence on the occurrence of any other [earlier or future] member.

³Generally, one of the core, or fundamental problems of any RNG or entropy source expressed algebraically. Also, a good reminder that attempts to produce randomness using anything but true disorder — such in the case of starting with definite numbers or seeds and following some definite, well-known algorithm, in a way, still taint the result of the RNG. More about this line of criticism is presented in [2]. It also creates a kind of *Chicken-Egg Problem* for RNGs — what should be worried about first? The source of the seed/entropy, or what to do with such “hopefully random” initial input once obtained?

And thus, if we were to simulate the generation or production of such sequences using a practical method such as the drawing of numbers from a bag or hat⁴, then, uniform distribution requires that at each draw, all the possible allowed numbers have equal chance of being drawn from the bag (e.g. drawer does not first inspect what is being drawn, and wont reject any value once it has been drawn).

Whereas, for statistical independence, in case one draw of a number from the bag occurs, then, to not bias subsequent draws, that number/tile/lot **must** remain present in the bag (or rather, is returned into the bag), so that it still can be drawn in subsequent draws. Also, the value of the digit or number drawn in the second or subsequent draws must not depend on or have anything to do with what was drawn earlier — i.e. early draws do not influence or bias nor determine future draws from the bag. And thus, each draw is independent of any other.

Further, the authors tell us that the **acceptable**, standard, statistical model of random digit generation must satisfy the following specification:

We are defining random digits by saying that they must conform to a particular statistical model: the digits are independent observations drawn from the discrete uniform distribution whose probability mass function is

$$Pr(r) = \frac{1}{10} \quad \forall r \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 9\} \quad (2)$$

Essentially, that for the 10 possible digits in the base-10 symbol set, ψ_{10} , that each digit must have the chance/probability of occurrence or that of being observed or chosen, that is equivalent to $\frac{1}{\mathcal{U}(\psi_{10})}$, and generally so we can say:

$$Pr(a_\beta) = \frac{1}{\mathcal{U}(\psi_\beta)} \quad \forall a_\beta \in \psi_\beta, \beta \geq 2 \quad (3)$$

Note that **Equation 3** leverages ideas that should now already be familiar for those who have read transformatics[3] and the GTNC paper[5].

0.3 Concerning Difficulty of Generating Random Numbers Directly from The Head

We encounter a warning, and one we shouldn't take for granted, concerning attempts to generate random numbers using mere thought or guesswork. We are told:

It is very difficult to produce a random sequence by writing down a run of numbers 'haphazardly' out of the head, because we tend not to follow any digit with the same digit again.

One would want to especially stress the point "*...because we tend not to follow any digit with the same digit again.*". Moreover, we are told:

In a list like this, there is often a lack of 00's, 11's and so on, and 000's, 111's, ..., 999's are usually much too rare.

⁴Essentially, the drawing of number-labeled lots.

And so, this lesson should be kept in mind when designing, but also evaluating not only random digit generators but otherwise randomness generators in general — see for example the RNG implemented and presented in **Section 8.3.4** of [4], and that such instances of repeated or redundant symbols occurring in the output of a true random number generator (tRNG) ought not be frowned on⁵.

0.4 Concerning Testing for Randomness

Next, we look at what this book says of how to go about empirically or theoretically testing for *the quality* of some RNG implementation or method.

First, we learn that the most simple of any such methods is the **Frequency Test**:

The simplest of these [methods] is the frequency test. This takes long runs [one or more pages] of digits [generated and printed] and examines whether each digit, 0, 1, . . . , 9 has equal frequency, within acceptable statistical limits.

Thus, for testing for the quality and correctness of a random number generator, we can note that; if it can be established that in a large sample of generated numbers using the RNG, any of the possible symbols (e.g. 0,1,2,...,a,b,c,..., x,y,z for ψ_{36}) has nearly equal or exactly the same chance of occurrence, then this **is sufficient proof** that the RNG is fair enough and not only correct but reliable and unbiased.

0.4.1 On Using the χ^2 -Test to Evaluate an RNG

This book too, offers a substantial treatment of how to evaluate random number generators using the traditional statistical test known as the **Chi-Square Test** — also usually denoted χ^2 -Test. We essentially learn how to leverage the test to determine if some RNG is indeed statistically fair and correct.

First, using the example of drawing digits randomly from a bag or hat as presented in earlier discourse, we find that, if we tabulate the results of recording the frequency of each digit's occurrence across a large enough sample of tests (e.g. if $N=1000$, to mean, we drew random digits using the chosen method for 1000 runs), then we can tabulate each digit observed and the total number of times it was observed across the experiment — a number we might denote O_r , and cast this against the total number of times we expected each digit or symbol to occur (refer to **Equation 1** and **Equation 3**), and this later quantity we might denote E_r .

So, note that, since each symbol has a chance of $\frac{1}{\mathcal{L}(\psi_\beta)}$ (which would be $\frac{1}{10}$ for each 'digit' in the case of ψ_{10}), then we expect that in ideal conditions, each such symbol should occur $N \times \frac{1}{\mathcal{L}(\psi_\beta)}$ — so in the case of random digits, we would expect $E_r = \frac{N}{10}$, and thus, for the case of $N = 1000$, should expect $E_r = 100$. In summary then, we would tabulate our observations and expectations as shown in the following table:

⁵Unless perhaps, and the exception being cases such as the generation of **random sets** — knowing that elements in a pure set ought be distinct and unrepeated — a good example would be generating random o-SSI[6].

r	0	1	2	3	...	9	Σ
O_r	106	89	97	101	...	91	1000
E_r	100	100	100	100	...	100	1000
$O_r - E_r$	6	-11	-3	1	...	-9	0
$(O_r - E_r)^2$	36	121	9	1	...	81	700
$\frac{(O_r - E_r)^2}{E_r}$	0.36	1.21	0.09	0.01	...	0.81	7.0

Table 1: Tabular Analysis of a Random Digit Generator using ξ^2 -Test during a particular experiment spanning 1000 observations

And thus, using the statistic presented as such:

$$\xi^2 = \sum_{r=0}^9 \frac{(O_r - E_r)^2}{E_r} \quad (4)$$

We are then able, as shown in **Table 1**, to arrive at some score, a measure, a metric, such as **7.0** in the chosen case, by which we might proceed to judge whether or not the underlying RNG was fair or not.

Before we leave Clarke et al, it shall be worth noting that, for the case of evaluating any RNG that produces numbers or symbols from some finite symbol set ψ_β , that one very useful generalization of the test depicted in **Equation 5** would be:

$$\xi^2 = \frac{\mathcal{N}(\psi_\beta)}{N} \sum_{\omega \in \psi_\beta} \left(O_\omega - \frac{N}{\mathcal{N}(\psi_\beta)} \right)^2 \quad \forall N \in \mathbb{N} \quad (5)$$

How to actually use the obtained score or ξ^2 value is covered well in [1] — see **Section 18.3.1**. However, concerning this, we might want to note that:

Obviously, we shall obtain a different value of ξ^2 each time we take a fresh sample of 1000 digits: ξ^2 has a sampling distribution in the sense defined in Chapter 15. On the assumption that the null hypothesis is true, we can find the sampling distribution of ξ^2 , at least approximately.

And finally, and concerning this particular case/example, that:

ξ^2 will be approximately distributed as $\xi_{(9)}^2$ if the null hypothesis is true. The computed value of ξ^2 was 7.00. By reference to Table A4 we see that such a value is by no means an unlikely one for a $\xi_{(9)}^2$ random variable, and we cannot reject the null hypothesis. On the evidence of this test, it is reasonable to regard the observed set of 1000 digits as random.

For those interested in what $\xi_{(9)}^2$ means or how it was arrived at, also consult **Section 5.3.1** of [7] in addition to **Section 18.3** of [1]. And further, note that [7], also by the author of this review, offers an alternative approach to how one might evaluate an RNG using a method somewhat inspired by, but otherwise fundamentally different from the ξ^2 -Test; the **ADM/ \hat{A} -Test**.

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